

REVIEW OF SIMULATION STUDIES FOR GRAIN DRYING IN DIRECT SUN AND SOLAR DRYERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the theoretical models of physical processes in a drying system and their suitability for modeling the drying system. Detail discussion on the relationships and data required in the simulation models were also presented.

KEY WORDS: Thin layer drying model; Deep bed drying model; Drying equations; Drying Curves;

INTRODUCTION

A simulation is the execution of a model, represented by a computer program that gives information about the system being investigated.

Solar drying systems must be properly designed in order to meet particular drying requirements of specific crops and to give satisfactory performance with respect to energy requirements (Steinfeld and Segal 1986). The prediction of drying rate of the specific crops under various conditions is important for the design of the drying systems. Full-scale experimentation for different products and system configurations is sometimes costly and not possible.

The use of a simulation model is a valuable tool for prediction of performance of solar drying systems (Steinfeld and Segal 1986). Many deep bed simulation models for natural convection solar grain dryers have been proposed (Ibrahim and Hansen, 1984; Bala and Ziauddin, 1990; Garg and Sharma, 1990; Bala 1994) to predict the drying of grain. Thin-layer drying equations are used in deep bed grain drying simulation models. Therefore the accuracy of prediction of the deep bed simulation model depends on how accurately the layer drying equations have been developed.

Modeling drying of crops under solar energy is a complex problem involving simultaneous heat and mass transfer in a hygroscopic nature of crop. Several researchers have presented various numerical models for moisture migration, considering diffusion as the primary transport mechanism.

(Dincer and Dost, 1997) presented a method to determine the moisture diffusion coefficient and moisture transfer coefficient for a solid object by employing the drying coefficient and lag factor. (Smith and Sokhansanj, 1990) have developed a natural convection heat transfer model in which the density of air was assumed to be a function of temperature and absolute humidity.

(Ratti and Crapiste, 1995) evaluated the heat transfer coefficient under forced convection from the data on crop drying and heat and mass balances. The experimental heat transfer coefficients were correlated by dimensionless expressions with Nusselt and Reynolds numbers. The experimental heat transfer coefficient values ranged from 25 to 90 W/m² K for potatoes, apples and carrots. (Anwar and Tiwari, 2001) evaluated the convective heat transfer coefficients for some crops under a simulated condition of forced mode in indoor open and closed conditions. (Anwar and Tiwari, 2001) determined the convective heat transfer under open sun drying by using the linear regression technique. Their study was limited to constant rate

drying from 11 to 13.30 h of the day. The single value of convective heat transfer was evaluated for each crop for the whole drying process.

DRYING SIMULATION MODELS

Much of the drying and conditioning of agricultural products is carried out by artificial means. Greater yields and the need for storage over long periods of time demand a high degree of control over various properties viz temperature and moisture content of the product. Mathematical modeling of various drying systems is important for optimum management and prediction of performance of design variations. The utility of mathematical models can further be appreciated by the fact that full-scale experimentation for different products and drying seasons (climates), corresponding to various management strategies is not possible. Through these models, the information available on drying characteristics of the drying products from conventional drying can be linked with solar dryers for accelerating their development. The present section deals with the theoretical models of physical processes in a drying system. Subsequent sections incorporate a detailed discussion on the relationships and data required in the simulation models.

Early attempts to simulate the grain-drying process were made by (Hukill 1947). Following this, numerous drying simulation models have been developed over the past several years. Based on the grain bed depth involved, these models are either: (1) thin-layer drying models or (2) deep-bed drying models. However, depending on the nature of the development of mathematical equations, the simulation models can be grouped as:

1. Diffusion models
2. Partial differential equation models
3. Simultaneous heat and mass transfer models
4. Logarithmic models
5. Equilibrium models
6. Semitheoretical models
7. Empirical models

THEORETICAL DRYING EQUATIONS

Numerous physical mechanisms have been proposed to describe the moisture transport within the capillary porous products. Following (Brooker *et al*, 1978), these are:

1. Liquid movement due to surface forces (capillary flow);
2. Liquid movement due to moisture concentration difference (liquid diffusion);
3. Liquid movement due to diffusion at moisture on the pore surfaces (surface diffusion);
4. Vapor movement due to moisture concentration difference (vapor diffusion);
5. Vapor movement due to temperature difference (thermal diffusion)
6. Water and vapor movement due to total pressure difference (hydrodynamic flow).

Based on the physical mechanisms given above, (Luikor, 1966) has given a set of partial differential equations which describe the drying process of porous capillary products.

THIN-LAYER DRYING MODELS

Thin layer drying equations contribute to the understanding of the drying characteristics of agricultural materials (Afzal and Abe., 2000). Thin layer drying models fall into three categories, namely theoretical, semi-theoretical and empirical (Ozdemir and Devres. 1999). The theoretical approach concerns either the diffusion equation or simultaneous heat and mass transfer equations. The semi-theoretical approach concerns approximated theoretical equations. The empirical equations are easily applied to drying simulation as they depend on experimental data (Afzal and Abe., 2000). Among these models, the

Theoretical approaches take into account only the internal resistance to moisture transfer while the semi-theoretical and empirical approaches consider only the external resistance to moisture transfer between the product and air (Parti 1993).

(Luikov 1996) described the moisture transfer in capillary porous materials such as cereal grains by a number of physical mechanisms of diffusion (liquid, vapor, surface, and thermal), capillary flow, and hydrodynamic flow. In addition, (Young 1969) considered a repeated evaporation and condensation of moisture in the pores. These theories resulted in a system of partial differential equations. A number of researchers used the partial differential equation models with simplifying assumptions. These partial differential equation models did not become very popular because of their complexity and large computational time involved.

The most commonly used relationship is a semi-theoretical equation analogous to Newton's law of cooling. (Lewis, 1921) proposed that the rate of drying is directly proportional to the difference between the moisture content of the material being dried and its moisture content at equilibrium with the surrounding air; that is,

$$dM/dt = -k(M - M_e)$$

where: M = average moisture content, dry basis (d.b.) (decimal); t = drying time (hr); k = drying parameter or constant (hr^{-1}); and M_e = equilibrium moisture content, d.b. (decimal).

The model assumes that all the resistance to moisture flow is concentrated in a layer at the surface of the material. The above equation may be integrated to:

$$MR = (M_f - M_e)/(M_i - M_e) = \exp(-kt)$$

where: MR = average moisture ratio, dimensionless; M_i = initial moisture content, d.b. (decimal); and M_f = final moisture content, d.b. (decimal).

This equation is known, though inaccurately (Bakker-Arkema, *et al*) as the drying equation. It is also known as the exponential or logarithmic model. A series of empirical relationships discussing grain-drying processes was also developed. The early model was developed by (Thompson 1967) for drying of shelled corn. Table 1 lists the several thin-layer drying models proposed by a number of investigators for various grains.

DEEP-BED DRYING MODELS

Products like cereal grains are rarely dried in thin layers. Instead, grains are dried either in stationary-deep beds, or in fluidize beds.

From the point of view of application, the simulation models for a drying process may be categorized in two types viz. high temperature and low temperature grain drying models. However, it has been noticed in the literature that the former type of models is relatively simpler. Knowing the amount of moisture contents of the product, the energy consumed throughout the drying process can be calculated. To the contrary, the situation is complex in case of low-temperature drying models in which additional care of various factors, like, ambient air conditions, depth of grains, air-flow characteristics, grain storage life and management strategy, has to be taken. It may also be mentioned here that the model for optimization of drying systems with respect to cost or energy efficiency must not use prohibitively large computer time. A compromise should, therefore, be found between using a very complex model which gives results with greater accuracy, and a simple one which neglects relevant factors.

For modeling a deep bed of grain, the grain bed is considered to be a series of thin layers placed one over the other. The outlet air conditions for one layer are used as the inlet condition for the layer above [Figure

1]. Thermodynamic relationships between the drying air and grain moisture are used in solving the heat, mass, and energy balance equations (Henderson and Henderso. 1968).

For low temperature, low airflow conditions, [Bloome and Shove 1971] assumed equilibrium between the drying air and the grain in each layer for a certain time period. Later, (Thompson 1972) improved the equilibrium model proposed by Bloome and Shove. Further modifications of equilibrium models were proposed by (Morey 1979) and (Mittal and Otten 1980) to obtain more accurate results. However, the models of Bloome and Shove and Thompson give reasonable results under conditions where the equilibrium assumptions are valid (Sharp 1982)

Due to the complicated nature of the drying phenomenon, the success of grain drying simulation models has only been marginal (Bakker-Arkema 1983). There are continuing efforts to improve the existing models by incorporating new or additional parameters to include the effects of grain moisture content, temperature and physical properties, and airflow rate, temperature, and humidity more accurately.

Drying-simulation models are used in obtaining optimum dryer design and operating conditions; and new models for different grains and grain conditions have been developed (Bakker-Arkema 1983). Optimizing the total system costs, as an aid to selecting the best suitable drying system for a given farming situation, has also been performed (Bakker-Arkema 1983). Recently, modeling efforts have been made toward optimal grain drying and storage facility selection based on harvesting strategies and other on-farm operations and economic

TABLE 1 Thin-layer drying models for different grains

Grain	Model	Constants
Barley	MR = exp (-K t _c)	K = 139.3 exp (-7676)/(T _c + 460)
Corn	MR = exp (-K t ₃ ^N)	K = -3.47 x 10 ⁻⁷ + (2.87 x 10 ⁻⁷ x T _c) N = 0.54 + 3.24 x 10 ⁻⁷ RH
	t = A ln(MR) + B[ln(MR)]'	A = -1.86178 + 0.00488 T _c , B = 427.3640 exp (-0.03301 T _c)
Rice	MR = exp(-K t/N)	K = 0.01579 + 0.0001746 T _c - 0.01413 RH N = 0.6545 + 0.002425 T _c + 0.07867 RH
Sorghum	t = A ln(MR) + B[ln(MR)]'	A = -25.87 + 0.3354 T _c - 0.001075 T _c ' for 80 < T _c < 160 A = 0.54 - 0.0017 T _c , for 160 < T _c < 240 B = 30.35 exp (-0.0180 T _c)
Soybean	MR = exp[-(K t _c) ^N]	K = -0.207 + 3.57 x 10 ⁻⁷ + 0.216 MC + 0.261RH + 3 .202 x 10 ⁻⁷ M; T _c N = 0.33 + 0.00238 RH + 0.00276 T _c .
Wheat	MR = exp(-K t _c)	K = 2000 exp (-9179/(T _c + 460))

Where:

MR = moisture ratio; M_i = initial grain moisture, % (w.b.); t₁ = drying time (sec); t₂ = drying time (min); t₃ = drying time (hr); T_c = drying air temperature (°C); and T_c = drying air temperature (°F).

CEREAL GRAINS

In general, grains contain small amount of moisture and, therefore, scarcely display a constant rate drying period unless they are harvested at a very immature state or have had water condensed or rained on their surface. If h_D be the mass - transfer coefficient, the rate of moisture migration may be written as follows:

$$\frac{dm_w}{dt} = \frac{h_D A}{R_v T_{abs}} (\rho v_{wb} - \rho v_{\infty}) \quad 11$$

Where v_{wb} represents the saturated vapour pressure at wet-bulb temperature.

FIGURE 1: Illustration of a deep bed as a series of thin layers

Where:

T and H are temperature and humidity ratio of drying air, respectively.

Subscripts n, n + 1, and n + 2 represent the corresponding grain layer. [From Morey, R. V., Keener, H. M., Thompson, T. L., White, G. M., and Bakker-Arkema, F. W., American Society of Agricultural Engineers, paper No. 78-3009, St. Joseph, Mich., 1978].

Alternatively, the rate of mass of water evaporated may also be determined as

$$\frac{dm_w}{dt} = \frac{hA}{h_{fg}} (T_\infty - T_{wb}) \quad 12$$

Where h refers to the convective heat transfer coefficient.

Using the above equations, the constant drying rate may precisely be calculated if surface area A and either of the transfer coefficients h_D and h are known. It may be noted, however, that the evaluation of these transfer coefficients sometimes becomes a complex problem because most of the products have irregular shapes. Apart from this, because the surface temperature of the products do not precisely represent the wet-bulb temperature, higher values of vapor pressure causes errors in the estimation of constant - rate drying.

HIGH MOISTURE FOOD:

Many agricultural products such as potatoes and sugar beets along with some fruits show constant rate drying behavior when dehydrated under constant ambient conditions.

OTHER MATERIALS

Some materials of industrial applications viz. soap, textiles, hydrophilic solids etc also show constant rate drying periods. When all the heat for moisture evaporation is supplied by heated air, a dynamic equilibrium is established between the rate of heat transfer to the material and the moisture evaporated from the surface. This can be represented by combining equations (11) - (12) viz.

$$\frac{dm_w}{dt} = \frac{hA(T_\infty - T_{wb})}{h_{fg}} = h_D A \Delta P$$

The convective heat transfer coefficient and the rate of mass evaporated for different air-flow direction is given in Table 14, where Cs represents the specific heat of moist air in BTU/lb °F.

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF SOLAR DRYING CURVES

The solar drying curves can be fitted with different moisture ratio equations (Table 2) [Yaldiz *et al* 2001]. Different drying experiments can be performed by using the solar tunnel drying at a particular wind velocity. Simultaneously, they can also be conducted at a far lower wind velocity under the sun. The moisture ratio (MR = M_t/M_0) may be taken instead of $MR = (M_t - M_e) / (M_0 - M_e)$ for mathematical modeling of the solar drying curves because of the continuous fluctuation of the relative humidity of the drying air during both the forced and natural solar drying processes (Yaldiz and Ertekin, 2001).

TABLE 2 Convective heat transfer coefficient (h) and rates of drying (dmw/dt) for constant rate period

Direction of air flow	h(BTU/hr ft ² °F) *	(dm _w /dt) (lb/hr)
Parallel to plane surfaces	0.0128 G _a ^{0.8}	$\frac{0.0128 G_a^{0.8} A}{H}$
Perpendicular to plane surfaces	0.37 G _a ^{0.37}	$\frac{0.37 G_a^{0.37} A}{H}$
Through circulation (for Reynolds number 300)	$\frac{0.37 G_a^{0.59} C_s}{D_p^{0.41}}$	$\frac{0.37 C_s a G_a^{0.59}}{H}$

It is particularly emphasized that the correlation coefficient (r) is one of the primary criteria to select the best equation to account for the variation in the solar drying curves of the dried samples (Guarte, 1996). In addition to r, the reduced χ -square, as the mean square of the deviations between the experimental and calculated values for the models, can be used to determine the goodness of the fit. The lower are the values of the reduced χ -square, the better is the goodness of fit (Yaldiz and Ertekin C, 2001). χ -square can be calculated as:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (MR_{exp;i} - MR_{pre;i})^2}{N - n}$$

Where MR_{exp;i} is the ith experimental moisture ratio, MR_{pre;i} the ith predicted moisture ratio, N, the number of observations and n, the number of constants.

The effects of the initial and final moisture content, drying air temperature, relative humidity and velocity on the drying constants have been investigated by many researchers [Guarte, R. C., 1996]. The relationship with drying air temperature of the constants and coefficients of the best suitable model can be determined. In order to select and determine the most suitable model for the product to be dried, non-linear regression analyses can be done by using the Statistica Computer Program.

TABLE 2 Mathematical models applied to the drying curves

Model no.	Model name	Model
1	Newton	MR = exp (-kt)
2	Page	MR = exp (- kt ⁿ)
3	Modified Page	MR = exp (-(kt) ⁿ)
4	Henderson and Pabis	MR = a exp (-kt)
5	Logarithmic	MR = a exp (-kt) + c
6	Two term	MR = a exp (-k ₀ t) + b exp (-k ₁ t)
7	Two-term exponential	MR = a exp (-kt) + (1 - a) exp (-kat)
8	Wang and Singh	MR = 1 + at + bt ²

SIMULATION MODELS FOR SOLAR -ASSISTED DRYERS

Most of the simulation models developed so far assume constant inlet conditions and, hence, can be applied to the conventional drying process only. However, in a dryer using solar energy as the heat source, the inlet air conditions are highly dependent on climatological parameters and hence are strong function of time. Several workers have considered the possible use of solar collectors as a source of supplemental heat but the thermal models of drying process for variable air inlet conditions has not received enough attention. Main lucane in the use of solar energy in conventional dryers possibly seems to be the exaggerated effect of weather on dryer performance. It is because when the ambient air is cool and moist; more heat energy is needed in the dryer but the heat output of the collector is low. Conversely also, when the ambient air is dry, the air obtained from the solar collector is likely to be very dry and hence much over drying may occur.

(Sabbah *et al* 1979) have extended the logarithmic model given by (Barre *et al* 1971]) to incorporate the time-varying inlet conditions. Sabbah's model was later on used by (Mishra and Keener 1980) to investigate the operating costs of a solar assisted in-bin dryer. (Baker-Arkema *et al* 1976) applied the p.d.e.(partial differential equation) model for a solar-assisted low temperature dryer. (Roa and Macedo 1976) have also developed the theoretical model for drying process of 'caricoa' beans; the model is based on the heat and mass transfer laws presented by (brooker *et al* 1978).

RELATIONSHIPS AND DATA REQUIRED FOR DRYING SIMULATION MODELS

There are many parameters, like equilibrium moisture content, drying constant, physical properties of agricultural products and moist air, storage and grain deterioration which are used in the simulation models. However, many of these properties are specific for various types of product and hence are to be determined by either empirical equations, theoretical formulations or experimental investigations. Relationships which are not dependent on grain type such as psychometric relationships are also sometimes required. Prediction of the drying performance by simulation models is a function of these parameters; therefore, their evaluation needs careful attention.

CONCLUSION

Mathematical modeling and computer simulation models for the drying systems have been highlighted for efficiency evaluation and optimizing of the design achievement. Also, described is how experimental data can be fitted to different drying models available in the literature, through statistical analysis.

Solar drying is a technology that can be exploited in Nigeria in the light of increasing population and the need to produce more food that can be safely stored for food security. Technologies in existence can be used by selected procedure, the limiting factors being cost and production levels on farms. A significant amount of research is needed to develop efficient solar dryers and design procedures. Activities of this kind can be accelerated by close collaboration between workers in the field.

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